

ROLE OF INDEPENDENT WORK OF STUDENTS IN EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

¹Ismatova Magruba Shaukatovna, ²Anvarova Ruxshona

¹Assistant of Physiology Department of Samarkand State Medical University

²Student of Samarkand State Medical University “Without known independent in no serious matter the truth can be found”

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7534202>

Abstract. *Independent work, its organization play an important role in teaching, as well as in the scientific and creative work of a university student. How well the student is prepared and included in independent activity depends on his success in studies, scientific and professional work. Independent work is not limited to homework alone, which is carried out in lecture classes, in the presence of a teacher and under his guidance. In pedagogical science, there are various approaches to the definition of independent work.*

Keywords : *independent work of students, professional activity, educational material.*

The main task of higher education is to form a creative personality of a specialist capable of self-development, self-education, and innovation. The solution to this problem is hardly possible only by transferring knowledge in a finished form from teacher to student. It is necessary to transfer the student from a passive consumer of knowledge to an active creator of knowledge, who is able to formulate a problem, analyze ways to solve it, find the optimal result and prove its correctness.

The analysis shows that independent work still does not have the proper organization, and professional self-education as an important factor in the formation of the personality of a future specialist does not occupy an appropriate place in his training. The study of the real state of independent work indicates that students have little command of general educational skills and abilities: note-taking, reviewing, analysis and synthesis of what has been read. When independently studying the educational material and primary sources, students find it difficult to highlight the main, the main, in the formulation of conclusions, in the development of their opinion, their assessment of what they read.

Active independent work of students is possible only if there is serious and stable motivation. The strongest motivating factor is preparation for further effective professional activity. The essence of independent work, in our opinion, consists in self-organization of understanding of the material being studied, extracted from various sources, in building a student's own point of view, his attitude to what has been studied, in determining the practical significance of the material studied.

Organization of independent work begins, especially with: determining the content and scope of independent work each course; establishing a certain dose of material for independent study in each topic for a specific period of time; determining the content of the workshop on the formation of students' skills of independent work; from an introductory lesson, during which the student gets acquainted with the program and the nature of the tasks, with the requirements that apply to independent work, assessment criteria, methodology for completing tasks, forms of control and timing.

Practice shows that the upbringing of a creative specialist is impossible without mastering the theoretical foundations of disciplines, developing students' skills to operate with theoretical knowledge in a practical setting, and use it in solving professional problems. The student should be able to answer questions, understand the proposed situation, determine the ways out of it, review or annotate a monograph, article, and conduct direct observation of production processes during practice. A variety of tasks for independent work, giving them not only informational, but also professional orientation, establishing a close connection between theory and engineering practice is the incentive that motivates to master the skills and abilities of independent work and contributes to the restructuring of the student's personality structure into the structure of a specialist's personality.

The effectiveness of a student's independent work as a criterion for the quality of pedagogical management of the educational process is determined by its development in two directions: in the level of mastering by the student in the process of self-preparation the ability to navigate in situations that simulate future professional activity through tasks-situations, special exercises, in using theory to solve practical standard tasks; the degree of students' involvement in research activities through the implementation of non-standard tasks and tasks of increased complexity and in real industrial practice with the maximum use of the life experience of students, orienting them towards future professional activities. The effectiveness of students' independent work is largely determined by the presence of active methods of its control.

Based on the above, we can say that independent work, by its very nature, presupposes the maximum activity of each student. It manifests itself in the organization of work, and in the use of purposeful perception, processing, consolidation, application of knowledge and in a conscious desire to turn the acquired knowledge into beliefs, to be steadily guided by them in their daily activities. Properly organized independent work of students is of great educational and educational value. It is a defining condition for achieving high results in learning, in the formation of moral qualities and, therefore, is both a means and a goal of learning.

Conclusion

We agree with those methods that require that, in addition to lectures and textbooks, the student also pays attention to special literature, electronic library, etc. and we believe that the student most fully and deeply perceives only the information that he himself used and improved in the process of his activity, and no one will force him to perceive and process it if he does not want to.

REFERENCES

1. Shamova T.I. Management of educational systems. M.: Alfa-M, 2007. 384 p.
2. Vlasenko A.A., Soboleva N.V., Sobolev S.V., Petryaeva I.Yu. The role of independent work in the student's educational process // Modern problems of science and education. - 2014. - No. 5.
3. Kukushkin V.S. Introduction to pedagogical activity: Textbook /. - Rostov n / Don: March 2018. - 217s.
4. Abasov Z. Design and organization of students' independent work. Higher education in Russia, - 2019. - No. 10. - p. 81-84.
5. Qizi T. J. I., Farrukh S. TREATMENT OF MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION AND FIRST AID // Science and innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. D3. – C. 317-320.

6. Shernazarov F., Azimov A. INCREASED BRAIN PRESSURE-CAUSES, SYMPTOMS, COMPLICATIONS, TREATMENT //Современная медицина: новые подходы и актуальные исследования. – 2021. – С. 73-77.
7. qizi Tohirova J. I., og‘li Ibragimov B. I., og‘li Shernazarov F. F. CONGENITAL HEART DISEASE-CAUSES, CLASSIFICATION, DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT, COMPLICATIONS, CONSEQUENCES //Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 84-89.
8. Mratbaevna W. N., Farrux S. The Structure of the Heart and its Physiology in Regular Athletes //Eurasian Scientific Herald. – 2022. – Т. 8. – С. 102-105.
9. Farhod o‘g‘li S. F. GASTRIT—SABABLARI, ALOMATLARI, TASHXISLASH, DAVOLASH, DORILAR, ASORATLARI, OLDINI OLISH //Лучший инноватор в области науки. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 103-107.
10. Фаррух Ш. и др. ПУТИ УСТРАНЕНИЯ САХАРНОГО ДИАБЕТА //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. D3. – С. 313-316.
11. V. Sarkisova, A. Numonova, R. Xegay АНТИБИОТИКОРЕЗИСТЕНТНОСТЬ ИЛИ БОРЬБА С ГЛОБАЛЬНОЙ УГРОЗОЙ XXI ВЕКА // SAI. 2022. №D8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/antibiotikorezistentnost-ili-borba-s-globalnoy-ugrozoy-hxi-veka> (дата обращения: 07.12.2022).
12. Sarkisova V., Xegay R. CAUSES, DIAGNOSIS, CONSERVATIVE AND OPERATIVE TREATMENT OF UTERINE MYOMA //Science and Innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 8. – С. 198-203.
13. V. Sarkisova, A. Numonova, R. Xegay АСПЕКТЫ СОСТОЯНИЯ ВЕГЕТАТИВНОЙ НЕРВНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ПРИ ГИПОКСИИ // SAI. 2022. №D8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/aspekty-sostoyaniya-vegetativnoy-nervnoy-sistemy-pri-gipoksii> (дата обращения: 07.12.2022).
14. ABOUT THE CAUSES OF ENDOMETRIAL HYPERPLASIA AND FORMS OF ENDOMETRIAL HYPERPLASIA
15. SV Vladimirovna - ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions, 2022
16. Саркисова В., Джуманов Б., Исроилова Г. Анализ репродуктивного и соматического здоровья женщин, госпитализированных по поводу гиперплазии эндометрия и маточных кровотечений //Журнал вестник врача. – 2014. – Т. 1. – №. 01. – С. 169-170.
17. Саркисова В., Абдурахманова К. Роль гормональных препаратов в терапии гиперпластических процессов эндометрия и в частности при миоме матки //Журнал вестник врача. – 2014. – Т. 1. – №. 01. – С. 167-168.
18. Саркисова В., & Абдурахманова, К. (2014). Астено - вегетативные нарушения, оценка качества жизни у женщин климактерического возраста с гиперпластическими процессами в матке. Журнал вестник врача, 1(01), 163–166. извлечено от https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/doctors_herald/article/view/4565
19. Sarkisova V., Xegay R., Numonova A. ENDOCRINE CONTROL OF THE DIGESTION PROCESS. GASTROINTESTINAL ENDOCRINE CELLS //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. D8. – С. 582-586.
20. V. Sarkisova, A. Numonova, R. Xegay АНТИБИОТИКОРЕЗИСТЕНТНОСТЬ ИЛИ БОРЬБА С ГЛОБАЛЬНОЙ УГРОЗОЙ XXI ВЕКА // SAI. 2022. №D8. URL:

- <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/antibiotikorezistentnost-ili-borba-s-globalnoy-ugrozoy-hxi-veka> (дата обращения: 11.01.2023).
21. V. Sarkisova, A. Numonova, R. Xegay АСПЕКТЫ СОСТОЯНИЯ ВЕГЕТАТИВНОЙ НЕРВНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ПРИ ГИПОКСИИ // SAI. 2022. №D8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/aspekty-sostoyaniya-vegetativnoy-nervnoy-sistemy-pri-gipoksii> (дата обращения: 11.01.2023).
 22. Джуманов Б. и др. Применение инструментальных методов исследование в диагностике острого аппендицита у беременных //Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины. – 2014. – №. 1 (77). – С. 9-12.
 23. Sarkisova V. ASPECTS OF THE STATE OF THE AUTONOMIC NERVOUS SYSTEM IN HYPOXIA //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. D8. – С. 977-982.
 24. V. Sarkisova, X. Regina РОЛЬ БРАДИКИНИНА В ПРОТЕКАНИИ ОСНОВНЫХ ЖИЗНЕННЫХ ПРОЦЕССОВ // SAI. 2022. №D8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/rol-bradikinina-v-protekanii-osnovnyh-zhiznennyh-protsessov> (дата обращения: 11.01.2023).
 25. Sarkisova V. et al. ESSENTIAL ROLE OF BRADIKININ IN THE COURSE OF BASIC LIFE PROCESSES //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. D8. – С. 576-581.
 26. Sarkisova V., Xegay R., Numonova A. ENDOCRINE CONTROL OF THE DIGESTION PROCESS. GASTROINTESTINAL ENDOCRINE CELLS //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. D8. – С. 582-586.